

ELECTRON-BEAM IRRADIATION OF RECYCLED NEWSPAPER FILLED POLYPROPYLENE/ NATURAL RUBBER COMPOSITES: EFFECT OF CROSSLINK PROMOTERS

H. Osman, H. Ismail, M. Mariatti
School of Materials and Mineral Resources Engineering
Universiti Sains Malaysia, 143000 Nibong Tebal, Penang, Malaysia
ohakimah@gmail.com

SUMMARY

The effect of crosslink promoters on electron-beam irradiation of recycled newspaper filled polypropylene/ natural rubber composites were studied. The results indicate that composites containing crosslink promoters (i.e, TMPTA or TPGDA) achieved better tensile strength (T_S) and Young's modulus compare to control (without crosslink promoters), with incorporation of the TMPTA caused the highest T_S and modulus of the composites at similar filler content. Meanwhile, E_B of the composites showed significant decrease in all cases with increasing filler content. A part from that, composites with the TMPTA caused the lowest elongation at break (E_B).

Keywords: electron-beam irradiation, recycled newspaper, polypropylene, natural rubber, trimethylol propane triacrylate, tripropylene glycol diacrylate

INTRODUCTION

The use of radiation in processing of polymers is gaining more interest because it can be suggested as an alternative to the traditional chemical method liked sulphur vulcanization, in order to modify molecular structure of polymers. The possibility of processing the final shape of the polymeric materials in the solid state opens up new opportunities to obtain materials with well tailored-properties [1]. The radiation is also function as a pasteurization method to sterilize materials, especially for any materials that very susceptible to microorganisms attack. For example, Shin *et al.* [2] have been studied on the effect of radiation to the protein, filtration efficiency and crude fiber degradation after sugar cane bagasse fermentation by mushroom fungi. Meanwhile, the filler used in this research study is natural fiber base materials filled PP/NR composites. Thus, the exposure of these composites to high energy radiation is not only to improve their properties but also can prevent fungal, microorganism and insect attack.

In recent years various radiation sources e.g., X-rays (soft and hard), gamma (γ), ultraviolet (UV) rays, electron beam (EB), cobalt and cesium are being used in the curing of various polymers, paints, ink, coatings, adhesives, etc. [3,4]. Polymeric substances which are predominantly high molecular weight organic compounds such as thermoplastics and elastomers, respond to radiation in several ways includes polymer modification. The polymer modification covers irradiation cross-linking (e.g. in wire

and cable industry, or plastic films), irradiation-induced polymerization (graft polymerization and curing), scission (e.g. degradation of PTFE) and also to sterilize medical products [5]. The irradiation of polymeric materials with ionizing radiation (gamma rays, X-rays, accelerated electrons, ion beams) leads to the formation of very reactive intermediates, free radicals, ions and excited states [6]. The EB source is chosen to crosslink the polymer composites in this research study. The most important part is the EB can be steered very easily to meet the requirements of various geometrical shapes of products to be irradiated. This cannot be achieved by X-rays and γ rays. In some applications, the high penetrating power of the EB allows the efficient curing of thick polymeric articles, highly pigmented inks and coatings. Pigmented inks and coatings cannot be otherwise cured by UV radiation due to low penetrating power [3].

However, irradiation at high irradiation dosage may lead to more chain scissions rather than crosslinking of the polymer chains. With addition of crosslink promoters as a multi functional monomers which are highly reactive towards free radicals with existence of peroxides, UV light and irradiation, it can suppresses the chain scission reaction and leads to efficient crosslinking. For this reasons, some of the polymer properties may be improved such as heat aging, modulus, tensile strength, tear strength, hardness, abrasion resistance, resilience, etc. [7]. The literature survey indicates that no work has been in the area of EB irradiation of RNP filled PP/ NR composites in presence of different crosslink promoters. The aim of this work was to examine the effectiveness of those two crosslink promoters (i.e., TMPTA and TPGDA) on mechanical properties and gel content of the radiation-induced crosslink of the RNP filled PP/ NR composites.

EXPERIMENTAL METHOD

Raw Materials

The RNPs were prepared in laboratory scale. The RNP which consists of about 97% organic components (cellulose, hemicellulose and lignin) with particle size of 23 μ m and density of 1.8 g/cm³ was used. Details of chemical component of the RNP can be seen in Table 1 [8]. Composites of 50/ 50 phr: PP: NR reinforced by different compositions of RNP (5, 10, 15 and 20 phr) were prepared in a Haake Polydrive with Rheomix R600/610 at temperature 160°C, rotor speed 50 rpm for 10 min. TMPTA or TPGDA at 3 phr were introduced separately into the mixer 1 min before the fibers were added. The formulation of those composites, with and without the crosslink promoters is given in Table 2. The samples were compression molded via preheating for 3 min followed by compressing for 3 min at 170°C. The moulded sheets were irradiated using a 3 MeV electron beam (EB) accelerator NHV EPS-3000 at a dose 40 kGy. Tensile properties of the composites were performed on an Instron 3366 at a cross head speed of 50 mm/min and according to ASTM D 412-92. The test results reported in this work were averaged from ten determinations. Degree of crosslinking can be determined by measuring the gel content.

Table 1 Elements of the RNP

Element	Wt (%)
Na ₂ O	0.45
MgO	0.093
Al ₂ O ₃	0.87
SiO ₂	0.91
SO ₃	0.014
K ₂ O	0.2
CaO	0.44
TiO ₂	Trace
Fe ₂ O ₃	Trace
LOI(Organic)	97.0

Table 2 Formulation of incorporation of the crosslink promoters to the RNP filled PP/ NR composites

Materials	Composition (phr*)
PP	50
NR	50
RNP	0, 5, 10, 15, 20
TMPTA/ TPGDA	3

*parts per hundred resin

The gel content of the crosslinked samples was determined by extraction of the samples in boiling xylene for 24 hours using Soxhlet apparatus. The extracted samples were dried in oven at 50°C till constant weight. The gel content was calculated as [9];

$$\% \text{ Gel content} = \frac{W_1}{W_0} \times 100$$

Where W_1 and W_0 are the weight of the dried sample after extraction and the weight of the sample before extraction, respectively.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Effects of Crosslink Promoters on Tensile Properties

Figures 1(a) and 2(b) show tensile properties of RNP filled PP/ NR composites as a function of filler content and crosslink promoter contribution. In all samples, the Young's modulus (Figure 1(a)) increases and the EB (Figure 1(b)) decreases with increasing filler content. However, the tensile strength (Figure 1(a)) increase at lower filler content and then slightly decreases at higher filler content. The tensile properties

provide an excellent measure of the degree of reinforcement provided by the fiber to the composites [11]. The tensile strength for composites with and without crosslink promoters show increment up to 10 phr and 5 phr, respectively, then decreases at higher filler content. The increasing trend indicates a considerable reinforcing effect from these fibers. While, the decreasing in tensile strength were probably caused by a number of reasons including: (i) irregular shaped of filler present, as can be seen in Figure 4, (ii) poor dispersion of the fibers in the matrix, (iii) moisture pick-up, and (iv) increases of interfacial defects or debonding between the fiber and the matrix [12]. This also due to the excessive crosslinking occurred with addition of TMPTA and TPGDA, thus reduces tensile strength. Meanwhile, the composites with TMPTA show the highest tensile strength and followed by composites with TPGDA and composites without crosslink promoters (control composites). It might be due to the ability of the TMPTA to reduce chain scission in order to achieve optimum tensile strength. Similar finding were reported by Khalid et al. [13]. The results are proportional with the trend observed for gel content (Figure 2).

In general the E_B of the composites (Figure 1(b)) follow the sequence of control > TPGDA > TMPTA >. As different with the tensile strength, the result of E_B is indirect proportional to the gel content. Papiya and Bhowmick [14] described the E_B reduces with increasing crosslink density, and thus limited extensibility of the composites. This observation reveals that the addition of the crosslink promoters have not improved the E_B as well as causing embrittlement to the composites, due to the high crosslink formed. It is interesting to note that the steep decreased in E_B at higher filler content may be due to low E_B of the fiber and this restrict the polymer molecules flowing past between each other. This behavior contributed to the decreased deformability of rigid interface between the filler and the matrix, by restricting the mobility of the polymer chains [8]. The lower E_B of the composites with crosslink promoters were associated with its larger stiffness, as well as dramatic increased in Young's modulus due to the rigidity of the composites [15]. Figure 1(a) show that the modulus increases with increasing filler content. It is also apparent in this figure that the modulus of the composites with TMPTA show the highest modulus, followed by composites with TPGDA and control composites. It is possible that the increase in stiffness upon addition of the crosslink promoters made the composites more brittle, due to the increase in crosslinking, as can be relates with the increase in gel content in all cases.

(a)

(b)

Figure 1. The effect of crosslink promoters on; (a) T_S and Young's modulus; and (b) elongation at break (E_B) of RNP filled PP/ NR composites.

Effects of Crosslink Promoters on Gel Content

Figure 2 shows the gel fraction of different systems of crosslink promoters. It can be seen that the both system, with and without crosslink promoters show a slight increases in gel content. The results explain that crosslink is gradually increases with increasing filler content. Usually, gel content is representing the degree of crosslinking of the samples; with higher value of the gel content would reflect greater degree of crosslinking. Since more crosslink occurred in the polymer chains, less solvent will be penetrated into the polymer molecules. It is found that from the experimental method of the gel content, extraction of the samples were done in boiling xylene for 24 hours using

Soxhlet apparatus. According to Vijayabaskar *et al.* [10], by increasing the extraction temperature, the mobility of the molecules and the generation of radicals are expected to increase and lead to more crosslinking. The same trend is seen in our results. The most important factor that contributes to this is the crosslink of the composites with addition of crosslink promoters. Obviously, composites with crosslink promoters show significant increase in gel content compared to control composites. Such an observation is expected as the TMPTA and TPGDA employed in this study is well known as reactive additive to form crosslink by an irradiation-induced free radical mechanism [16].

Figure 2 Effect of different crosslink promoters to the irradiation induced-crosslink for RNP filled PP/ NR composites

CONCLUSIONS

The analysis of tensile properties and gel content show the better occurrence of irradiation-induced crosslink with and without TMPTA and TPGDA in RNP filled PP/NR composites.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors are grateful to the MINT for giving opportunities to undergo irradiation process.

References

1. C., Albano, J., Reyes, M., Ichazo, J., Gonzalez, M., Hernandez, M., Rodriguez. Mechanical, Thermal and Morphological Behaviour of the Polystyrene, Polypropylene (80/20) Blend, Irradiated With γ -Rays at Low Doses (0-70kGy). *Polymer Degradation and Stability*, 2003, 80: 251-261.

2. H., -S., Shin, Ji, -H., Lee, E., -J, Hwang, J., -S., Shon, G., -N., Kim, S., Matsushashi, T., Kume. Radiation and NRSP Effect on protein, Filtration Efficiency and Crude Fiber Degradation After Sugar Can Bagasse Fermentation by Mushroom Fungi. *Radiation Physics and Chemistry*, 1998, 53: 571-575.
3. S., K., Datta, T., K., Chaki, A., K., Bhowmick. Electron Beam Processing of Polymers. In *Advanced Polymer Processing Operations* (Cheremisinoff, N. P., ed.), 1998, Noyes Publication, New Jersey
4. J., G., Drobny. *Radiation Technology for Polymers*, 2003, CRC Press LLC, Florida.
5. A., Singh, & K., Bahari. Use of High-Energy Radiation in Polymer Blends Technology. In *Polymer Blends Handbook. Volume II* (Utracki, L. A., ed.), 2002, Kluwer Academic Publishers, Netherlands.
6. A., G., Chmielewski, M., Haji-Saeid, S., Ahmed. Progress in Radiation Processing of Polymers, 2005, *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research B*, 2005, 236: 44–54.
7. B., Likozar, M., Krajnc. Influence of Morphology on the Dynamic Mechanical Properties of Hydrogenated Acrylonitrile Butadiene Elastomer/Coagent Nanodispersions. *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, 2008, 110: 183–195.
8. H., Osman, H., Ismail, M., Mariatti. The Effect of Recycled Newspaper Content and Size on the Properties of Polypropylene (PP)/Natural Rubber (NR) Composites. *Polym. Plastics Technol. & Eng.*, 2008, 47:23-29.
9. M. Zurina, H. Ismail, C.T. Ratnam. Characterization of Irradiation-Induced Crosslink of Epoxidised Natural Rubber/ Ethylene Vinyl Acetate. *Polymer Degradation and Stability*, 2006, 91(11): 2723-2730
10. V., Vijayabaskaran, M., Stephan, S., Kalaivani, S., Volke, G., Heinrich, H., Dorschner, A., K., Bhowmick, U., Wagenknecht. Influence of Radiation Temperature on the Crosslinking of Nitrile Rubber by Electron Beam Irradiation. *Radiation Physics and Chemistry*, 2008, 77: 511-521.
11. A., Karmarkar, S., S., Chauhan, J., M., Modak, M., Chanda, M. Mechanical Properties of Wood-Fiber Reinforced Polypropylene Composites: Effect of A Novel Compatibilizer With Isocyanate Functional Group, *Composites Pat A*, 2007, 38: 227-233.
12. T., A., Bullions, R., A., Gillespie, J., Price-O Brien, A., C., Loos. The Effect of Maleic Anhydride Modified Polypropylene on the mechanical Properties of Feather Fiber, Kraft Pulp, Polypropylene Composites, *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.*, 2004, 92: 3771-3783.
13. M., Khalid, A., Salmiaton, C., T., Ratnam, C., A., Luqman. Effect of Trimethylolpropane Triacrylate (TMPTA) on the Mechanical Properties of Palm Fiber Empty Fruit Bunch and Cellulose Fiber Biocomposite. *Journal of Engineering Science and Technology*, 2008, 3(2): 153-162.
14. S., M., Papiya, A., K., Bhowmick. Structure Property Relationship of Electron Beam Modified EPDM Rubber. *J. Applied Polym. Sci.*, 2000, 77: 323-337.

15. A., J., Nunez, P., C., Sturm, J., M., Kenny, M., I., Aranguren, N., E., Marcovich, M., M., Reboredo. Mechanical Characterization of Polypropylene-Wood Flour Composites, *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.*, 2003, 88: 1420-1428.
16. C. T., Ratnam, M., Nasir, A., Baharin, K., Zaman. Electron Beam Irradiation of Epoxidized Natural Rubber. *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research B*, 2001, 171: 445-464.